

ECONOSCITECH INTEGRATION

ISSUE
6

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC
ELECTRONIC JOURNAL

TASHKENT STATE
UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS

American University
of Technology

Powered by Arizona State University®

ISSN: 3060-5075

Acceptance of articles
PUBLISHED MONTHLY

ARTICLE CONTRIBUTORS
PROFESSORS, SCHOLARS,
SPECIALISTS, AND RESEARCHERS

Google
Scholar

Academic
Resource
Index
ResearchBib

BASE

OpenAIRE

doi
Digital
Object
Identifier

OPEN ACCESS

CONTACT:

+998 94 3540880

<https://econoscitech-integration-journal.uz>

2026

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna
DSc., Dean of Tourism Faculty, TSUE

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Suyunov Dilmurod Xolmurodovich
Doctor of Economics (DSc), Professor,

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Allayarov Shamsiddin Amanullayevich
doctor of economics (DSC), professor

RESPONSIBLE SECRETARY:

Otaboyev Axmed Maxsudbek o'g'li
TSUE independent researcher

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR
ELECTRONIC JOURNAL
"ECONOSCITECH-INTEGRATION"
HAS BEEN REGISTERED UNDER
THE NUMBER C-5669651 BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND
MASS COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA)
OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN,
EFFECTIVE FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

In accordance with Resolution No. 384/6 dated April 10, 2026, issued by the Presidium of the Supreme Attestation Commission under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this journal is included in the list of recommended international scientific publications for publishing the primary research findings of doctoral dissertations in the field of Economic Sciences.

Partners: Tashkent State University of Economics / American University of Technology in Tashkent (AUT)

Electronic publication, Issue 6. 374 pages.
Approved for publication on Iyun, 2026.

Editorial Board Members:

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Teshabayev To'liqin Zakirovich,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Said Irandoust,
Doctor of Chemical Engineering Sciences,
Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich,
Doctor of Economics, (DSc), Professor

Tokunaga Masahiro,
professor, PhD of Economics of the Faculty of
Business and Commerce

Debasis Das,
professor Department of Computer Science

Nitin Goje,
professor and Program Lead - Computer Science

Nargizakhon Shamshieva
Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Rakhmonov Norim Razzakovich,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Bayxonov Bahodirjon Tursunbayevich
Doctor of Science (DSc), Professor

Shomurodov Ravshan Tursunkulovich,
PhD, Associate Professor

Boymuratov Abduraxmat Djumayevich
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics

Sharopova Nafosat Radjabovna
DSc, Associate Professor

Sultanova Kamila Mukhtorali Kizi
Master of Science

CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR IMPLEMENTING TECHNOLOGICAL AND DIGITAL INNOVATIONS.....	10
Shakirxodjayeva Zuxra Rustamxanovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING INVESTMENT PROCESSES IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	16
Aliyeva Zilola Mamatvalyevna	
CURRENT STATE AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICE SECTORS IN TASHKENT CITY.....	23
Abdikayumov Bekzod Turdiniyozovich	
GREEN BONDS VS. SUSTAINABILITY LINKED LOANS: WHICH WORKS FOR INDUSTRIAL DECARBONISATION?	29
Ataxanov Umidbek Olimovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬЮ БАНКА.....	34
Маликова Дилрабо Муминовна	
ECONOMETRIC MODELLING OF FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	42
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
AN INTEGRAL INDEX METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE INVESTMENT POTENTIAL OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES	49
Sayyora Bakhtiyorovna Nazirova	
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЕ, ПУБЛИЧНЫЕ И ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ: ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ГРАНИЦЫ И ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ.....	53
Срождидинова Зарина Хайриддиновна	
BLOCKCHAIN-BASED FINANCIAL TRANSACTION MONITORING SYSTEM (SMART CONTRACTS, DECENTRALIZED DATABASE, AND AUDIT TRAILS).....	58
Olimova Mukhlisa Vohidjon qizi	
FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A DRIVER OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: REGIONAL DISPARITIES AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	65
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN STATISTICAL INDICATORS OF LABOR RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN SURXONDARYO REGION.....	72
Haydarova Dinora Atamurot qizi	
ASSESSING THE ROLE OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH ACROSS THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN USING INTENSITY COEFFICIENTS AND CLUSTER ANALYSIS.....	77
Anvarkhonov Abdulatifikhon Jamshidkhon ugli	
TECHNICAL, ECONOMIC, AND ENVIRONMENTAL EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING AGRIVOLTAIC SYSTEMS IN UZBEKISTAN	85
Jabborov Shaymurod Akram o'g'li	
Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li	
Atoyeva Mohinur Amrilloevna	
Avazov Jonibek Azizbek o'g'li	
МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА НА ТРАЕКТОРИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	91
Хазраткулова Лола Нармуминовна	
FINANCING GREEN PROJECTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: STATUS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS	97
Qorriyeva Shahnoza Safarbayevna	

FORMULA-BASED DISTRIBUTION OF INTERGOVERNMENTAL TRANSFERS TO LOCAL BUDGETS IN UZBEKISTAN: A COMPARATIVE SIMULATION ANALYSIS BASED ON 2026 FORECAST INDICATORS.....	103
Umidjon Pardaev Sarvar Maxmudov	
GOVERNMENT FUNDING AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES: FINANCIAL PROMOTION MECHANISMS.....	115
Bahriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
FORECASTING EXPORT AND IMPORT INDICATORS OF BUKHARA REGION	122
Ergashev Mirjon Yorqin o'g'li	
A CUSTOMER-ORIENTED INTEGRATIVE METHODOLOGICAL MODEL FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST SERVICES IN THE TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY	130
Bakayev Ziyovuddinkhan Toshbolta ogli	
A PESTLI ANALYSIS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM	139
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT STATUS AND EXPORT ACTIVITIES OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN	146
Khikmatullayeva Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi	
CHANGE MANAGEMENT DURING QUALITY ASSURANCE REFORM IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	154
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
СТРАТЕГИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПАЛОМНИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	162
Каримова Дилафруз Садриддин кизи	
E-COMMERCE AS A DIGITAL FORM OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INCREASING HOUSEHOLD INCOMES	167
Eshbayeva Shahnoza Fakhriddinovna	
ADVANTAGES OF IMPLEMENTING AN OCCUPATIONAL AND SKILLS MAPPING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN'S LABOUR MARKET	172
S.B.Goyipnazarov S.M.Kurbanbaeva	
ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF FIXED ASSETS UTILIZATION IN RAILWAY ENTERPRISES: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	178
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO ASSESSING RESOURCE USE IN THE CONTEXT OF A GREEN ECONOMY.....	183
Karimov Islombek Bekpolat o'g'li	
THE IMPACT OF ECOTOURISM ON REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT	
Samiev Siroj Saitovich Ochilova Guli Rashid kizi	
THE IMPACT OF RISK ALLOCATION ON INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP (PPP) PROJECTS	197
Khaydarova Charos Nizomiddinovna	
PROSPECTS FOR CHANGING THE VOLUME OF GRAPE CULTIVATION DUE TO THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE VITICULTURE COMPLEX.....	202
Bohtaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ.....	209
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
ENHANCING FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT INFLOWS IN THE POST-CRISIS ERA:	

AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	215
Foziljon Rustamov Xazratkulovich	
CURRENT STATE AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	219
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
THE PECULIARITIES OF USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST AND RECREATIONAL AREAS.....	225
Makhliyo Umarova	
CHALLENGES OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN HUMAN CAPITAL AND STRATEGIES FOR THEIR RESOLUTION.....	231
Aloviddin Zayniddinov Zayniddin ugli	
ANALYSIS OF THE EXPERIENCE OF SUCCESSFUL AGROTOURISM DESTINATIONS IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES: RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UZBEKISTAN.....	237
Aktamov Olimjon Abdugani o'g'li	
ASSESSING THE EFFICIENCY OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES EXPORT AT THE REGIONAL LEVEL.....	247
Alimova Shamsiya Abidovna	
ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF BUSINESS ENTITIES AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE FACTORS SHAPING IT: THE CASE OF BUKHARA REGION.....	254
Djurayeva Munira Sadilloevna	
THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE ECONOMY OF BUKHARA REGION AND THEIR DEVELOPMENT TRENDS: AN ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES AND REGIONAL CONCENTRATION.....	261
Azizjon Anvarovich Kadirov	
Nigina Djurayevna Yusupova	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF BORDER TRANSPORT SYSTEMS.....	268
Ikromov Elyor Ibodulloevich	
ПУТИ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ АУДИТОРСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	273
Бобонарова Камола	
GREEN BONDS AND SOVEREIGN DEBT INSTRUMENTS FOR INFRASTRUCTURE ASSET RENEWAL: AN ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL MECHANISMS.....	278
Suleimanov Farrukh	
ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL EXPERIENCES.....	286
Qudratova Gulzoda Mahmudovna	
THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	291
Munisa Abdurakhmonova	
ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH BASED ON THE COBBDOUGLAS PRODUCTION FUNCTION: A CASE STUDY OF SURXONDARYA REGION.....	296
Turaev Bakhtiyor Ergashevich	
GENERAL APPROACHES TO COST REDUCTION IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	302
Kamola Saidova	
СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ И ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ВНУТРЕННЕГО АУДИТА В БЮДЖЕТНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ.....	307
Сайтмуратов Сайтмурат Машарип угли	
A CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF THE IMPACT OF INTERMEDIATION SERVICES ON BANK PERFORMANCE AND ITS STATISTICAL RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	314
Miraxmedov Jasur Isroilovich	
EMPLOYER BRANDING IN UZBEKISTAN: HOW TO BECOME AN EMPLOYER OF CHOICE FOR TALENT.....	320
Doniyorova Fotimabonu Alisher qizi	

FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH.....	325
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	331
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF ACCOUNTING AND ANALYSIS OF MATERIAL COSTS IN OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY ENTITIES BASED ON MODERN MANAGEMENT REQUIREMENTS.....	336
Sa'dullayeva Sayyora Nasillo qizi	
ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC APPROACHES AND BARRIERS TO THE INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	341
Samieva Gulnoza Tokhirovna	
THE IMPACT OF EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION OF LABOR POTENTIAL ON THE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF A REGION (A case study of the Khorezm region).....	348
Kutlimuratov Mansurbek Sattarovich	
CHARACTERISTICS OF CLUSTERING TEXTILE ENTERPRISES.....	354
Asadbek Eshniyozov	
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND CAPACITYBUILDING IN DEVELOPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY: A THEORETICAL AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS	358
Abdullaev Azamat Akbar o'g'li	
THE ROLE OF 5G TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE OF TELECOMMUNICATION ENTERPRISES	366
Saidqosimova Umida Ibragimovna	
DIGITAL PLATFORMS AND THE EFFICIENCY OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	371
Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich	
MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTEREST RATE RISK MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	377
Seitnazarov Daniyar Bakhadyrovich	
METHODOLOGY AND WAYS OF EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.....	385
Shodmonkulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
MAIN DIRECTIONS AND PROSPECTS FOR THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF INVESTMENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF TRANSFORMATION	391
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.....	395
Shodmonkulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ РЕГИОНОВ КАК ФАКТОР ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	399
Бутаева Сабина Холиёровна	
THE ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGIES IN INCREASING THE BRAND CAPITAL OF TOURISM ENTERPRISES	404
Zufarov Akmal Gulamiddinovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECT FINANCING UNDER PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS (PPP)	416
Shodiev Akmal O'ktamjon ugli	
IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT OF THE INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT	422
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
BLOCKCHAIN AND IOT FOR DIGITAL TRACKING OF FOOD EXPORTIMPORT FLOWS.....	426
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna	
Najmiddinov Yakhyo Fazliddin ugli	

THE PAYBACK PERIOD METHOD IN PERSONAL FINANCE: APPLICATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR FINANCIAL DECISION-MAKING	438
Akhunova Elena Anvarovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF AN ADAPTIVE FIBONACCI STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS MODEL FOR GOLD TRADING: EVIDENCE FROM THE XAU/USD MARKET	447
Tukmirzaev Kamol Mumin ugli	
DEVELOPING MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN RETAIL TRADE THROUGH A BRAND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM: DIRECTIONS AND STRATEGIC PRIORITIES.....	455
Shohboz Ro‘zimatov Hamdambek o‘g‘li	
MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	461
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH.....	466
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ НАУЧНЫХ ВЗГЛЯДОВ НА РОЛЬ СФЕРЫ УСЛУГ В ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	472
Усманов Фарзод Шохрухович	
STRATEGIC INSIGHTS FOR UZBEKISTAN’S RURAL DIGITALIZATION: LESSONS FROM THE SPATIAL SPILLOVER EFFECTS OF CHINA’S DIGITAL ECONOMY	481
Zhang Zhe	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ	487
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING SERVICE INFRASTRUCTURE EFFICIENCY: EVIDENCE FROM KASHKADARYA REGION	493
Azimov Islom	
ASSESSING DIGITAL GOVERNANCE EFFECTIVENESS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	498
Berdiyev Temurbek Makhmudullo ugli	
РАЗРАБОТКА ИНТЕГРАЛЬНОГО ИНДЕКСА КОРПОРАТИВНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ (CGI) ДЛЯ БАНКОВ С ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫМ УЧАСТИЕМ.....	506
Жумадуллаева Дурдона Шухрат кизи	
DIGITAL ECONOMY-BASED GOVERNANCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: LEVERAGING AI AND DATA FOR IMPROVED INSTITUTIONAL PERFORMANCE	512
Olimjonov Abbosjon Olimjonovich	
THE IMPACT OF E-COMMERCE DEVELOPMENT ON NATIONAL ECONOMIC COMPETITIVENESS.....	517
Baymuradov Shokhrukh Makhmudovich	
FACTORS INFLUENCING TAX REVENUE EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONTEXT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT.....	522
Jurayev Xusan Atamuratovich	
THE ESSENCE, TASKS, AND INTERNATIONAL APPROACHES OF INTERNAL AUDIT IN LEASING TRANSACTIONS.....	536
Sadritdinov Bakhodir Bakhtiyarovich	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING IN THE MINING SECTOR.....	543
Oybekova S.K.	
METHODOLOGY FOR REFLECTING GOODWILL, INTANGIBLE ASSETS, AND INVESTMENTS IN CONSOLIDATION.....	548
Maxmudova Nargiza Davlyat qizi	
FACTORS AFFECTING DAIRY PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY:	

CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS.....	554
Ergashev M.Y.	
Tairova Z.M.	
THE DMED INFORMATION SYSTEM AS A FOUNDATION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL E-HEALTH SYSTEM	561
Omonov Olim Murodullayevich	
THEORETICAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS FOR ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN GLOBAL MARKETS	566
Safarova Muxabbat Radjabovna	
THEORETICAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SUPPLY SYSTEM OF NURSERY FARMS	573
Abdufarmonov Farrux Faxriddinovich	
APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TOURISM MARKET AND ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE PLATFORM ECONOMY.....	580
Jumayev Bobomurod Nurmaxmat o'g'li	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ «ЖЕНСКОГО» ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА В ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЕ.....	586
Холбаева Сабина Рустамовна	
ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ПРИОРИТЕТНЫХ НАПРАВЛЕНИЙ ПОДДЕРЖКИ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ С УЧЁТОМ ЗАРУБЕЖНОГО ОПЫТА В МАЛОМ И СРЕДНЕМ БИЗНЕСЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	595
Камбарова Шахнозахон Мирвахитовна	
ISSUES OF EFFECTIVELY UTILIZING REGIONAL EXPORT POTENTIAL IN UZBEKISTAN	603
Umaraliyev Sarvar Rustamovich	
TERRITORIAL DISPROPORTIONS IN TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE OF THE JIZZAKH REGION AND THEIR IMPACT ON TOURIST FLOWS.....	610
A.Sh. Daliev	
T.Sh. Muxiddinov	
METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO HOUSING CONSTRUCTION DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN: INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY AND PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP MECHANISMS.....	616
Mirumar Abdulla Ugli Usmonov	
IMPROVEMENT OF COST ACCOUNTING AND ECONOMIC ANALYSIS IN THE FISHERY INDUSTRY: PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR THE ADAPTATION OF IFRS, ECONOMETRIC MODELING, AND ESG REPORTING FOR FISHERY CLUSTERS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	620
Shodiev Aslam Rakhmatilloevich	
Alikulov Abdumumin Ismatovich	
WAYS TO DEVELOP FRUIT PROCESSING ENTERPRISES BASED ON THE CLUSTER SYSTEM	627
Yusufova Laylo G'ayrat qizi	
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN MODERN BANKING SERVICE DEVELOPMENT	635
Mamutova Ayygul Kalmurzaevna	
IMPLEMENTATION OF COMPUTER-ASSISTED AUDIT TECHNIQUES (CAATS) AND ANALYTICAL PROCEDURES IN THE AUDIT OF COMMERCIAL BANKS' FINANCIAL STATEMENTS.....	642
Ibragimov Nodirbek Baxodir ugli	
CRITERIA FOR ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF THE AUDIT OF COMMERCIAL BANKS' FINANCIAL STATEMENTS AND THE FORMATION OF KEY AUDIT MATTERS (ISA 701)	649
Ibragimov Nodirbek Baxodir ugli	
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND CAPACITYBUILDING IN DEVELOPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY: A THEORETICAL AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS	656
Abdullayev Azamat Akbar o'g'li	

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN SERICULTURE DEVELOPMENT: ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS APPLICABLE TO UZBEKISTAN.....	664
Janikulova Lobar Shakarbaevna	
SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE THROUGH ESG AND ENERGY MANAGEMENT: A GREEN MARKETING PERSPECTIVE	670
Khaydarova Kamola Axinjanovna	
SYSTEM AND STRATEGY FOR HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT IN AN ORGANIZATION	675
Azimov Tolmas Nematullayevich	
MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF SMALL BUSINESSES: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	682
Abdusalim Shavkatov	
STRUCTURE AND DYNAMICS OF BANK LOANS	689
Jorayeva Zarifa	

STRUCTURE AND DYNAMICS OF BANK LOANS

Jorayeva Zarifa

Doctoral Student, Department of Finance,

Termez State University

ORCID: 0009-0009-1939-2394

Abstract. This article analyzes the structure and dynamics of credit services provided by commercial banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The study examines the main areas of the lending system, including the financing of small businesses, consumer loans, mortgage loans, and digital lending processes. In addition, the article considers existing problems in lending practice and proposes ways to address them.

Keywords: commercial banks, lending, loan portfolio, mortgage loan, consumer loan, digital banking services, credit risks, financial literacy.

Аннотация. В статье анализируются структура и динамика кредитных услуг, предоставляемых коммерческими банками Республики Узбекистан. Изучаются основные направления системы кредитования, включая финансирование малого бизнеса, потребительские кредиты, ипотечное кредитование, а также процессы цифрового кредитования. Кроме того, рассматриваются существующие проблемы кредитной практики и предлагаются пути их решения.

Ключевые слова: коммерческие банки, кредитование, кредитный портфель, ипотечный кредит, потребительский кредит, цифровые банковские услуги, кредитные риски, финансовая грамотность.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of globalization, the banking system is one of the most important sectors of the economy [17]. As a result of ongoing reforms and modernization measures implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the lending activities of commercial banks have reached a new stage of development [8]. Credit services play an important role in stimulating economic growth, attracting investment, and improving the living standards of the population [17].

LITERATURE REVIEW

A number of laws and subordinate regulatory documents related to the research topic were examined in detail. In particular, the adoption of the new edition of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated November 11, 2019, as well as the new edition of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Banks and Banking Activity” dated November 5, 2019, indicates that the banking and financial sector of the country is being consistently reformed. As a result, a number of measures are being implemented to create the necessary legal conditions for conducting modern banking activities and strengthening the competitive environment in this sector [1; 2; 8].

In addition, the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. LRU-765 “On Non-Bank Credit Organizations and Microfinance Activities” dated April 20, 2022, systematized the norms regulating the activities of microcredit organizations, pawnshops, and mortgage refinancing organizations that have the right to carry out certain types of financial operations. The law also defines the list of financial services provided by non-bank credit organizations, taking into account the specific features of their activities [4].

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Payments and Payment Systems” dated November 1, 2019, also plays an important role in the development of the financial services market [3]. This law serves as the legal basis for regulating relations between individuals and legal entities that act as payment service providers and payment service users in the process of making payments and providing payment services.

One of the important issues of the credit mechanism is the organization of reserve allocations intended to cover possible losses arising from loans [10]. According to Instruction No. 2696 of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 14, 2015, “On the Procedure for Classifying the Quality of Assets in Commercial Banks and Forming and Using Reserves to Cover Possible Losses on Assets”, the transfer of

“hopeless” assets and accrued interest on them from balance sheet accounts to off-balance-sheet accounts does not mean the cancellation of debts on these assets and interest on them. Therefore, such debt and accrued interest must be reflected in off-balance-sheet items for a period of not less than five years from the date of transfer to these accounts.

If the debt on an asset recorded in off-balance-sheet items is not paid by the debtor within five years after being transferred to these accounts, despite all measures taken by the commercial bank to collect the debt, the asset, including both the principal debt and accrued interest, may be written off based on the decision of the Council of the commercial bank approved at the general meeting of shareholders.

Reserve allocations are formed for all five categories of classified loans, and the rates are established as follows: standard loans — 1%; substandard loans — 10%; unsatisfactory loans — 25%; doubtful loans — 50%; and hopeless loans — 100%.

Another important issue of the credit mechanism is the establishment of prudential requirements for the lending activities of commercial banks by the authorities supervising the banking sector. In accordance with the Law “On the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, the Central Bank establishes restrictions on transactions with persons related to banks, including the granting of loans to such persons. It also determines the procedure for calculating prudential standards and the permissible values of these standards for banks, including systemically important banks, as well as banking groups, microfinance organizations, and mortgage refinancing organizations.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to assess the current state of the credit mechanism, this study analyzes indicators characterizing the structure and dynamics of loans issued by commercial banks, as well as their profitability and credit risk levels.

The analysis is based on official statistical data from the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan and financial statement data from the commercial banks selected as the objects of the research [11; 12; 15; 16].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 1

Structure of assets of commercial banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in percent¹

Asset structure	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Cash assets, including:	17.3	18.1	20.0	15.1	16.3
Cash in hand and other payment documents	2.7	2.4	3.5	2.3	3.1
Funds in the Central Bank	5.1	7.1	6.6	3.7	5.1
Funds in other resident banks	3.6	3.0	3.1	3.9	3.7
Funds in other non-resident banks	5.9	5.6	6.8	5.2	4.4
Investments in securities	2.6	4.4	5.7	5.0	5.0
Liabilities on customers' financial instruments	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.5
Loans	73.8	71.1	68.1	71.2	70.2
Fixed assets	2.3	2.5	2.6	2.9	3.0
Accrued interest on assets	2.2	2.1	2.2	3.1	3.0
Other assets	1.4	1.5	1.1	2.3	2.0
Total assets	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

As can be seen from the data in Table 1, loans accounted for the largest share of the total assets of commercial banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan during 2020–2024. This indicates that lending remained the main area of activity for commercial banks in the country during the analyzed period.

The data in Table 1 also show that investments in securities accounted for a relatively small share of the assets of commercial banks in Uzbekistan in 2020–2024. From the perspective of diversifying banking activities and strengthening the role of banks in the development of the national economy, this situation requires further improvement. In developed countries, investments in securities are considered an important condition for ensuring the financial stability and liquidity of commercial banks.

The sectoral structure of loans is analyzed in Table 2.

¹ author's development

Table 2
Sectoral structure of loans of commercial banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in percent²

Sectors	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Industry	36.9	36.0	32.5	29.7	28.8
Agriculture	10.1	10.7	10.8	10.0	9.4
Construction	2.7	2.8	2.7	2.6	2.4
Trade and general services	7.2	8.4	7.4	6.9	7.2
Transport and communication	9.6	8.8	7.6	7.3	6.2
Material and technical supply	1.4	1.2	1.0	0.9	0.8
Housing and communal services	1.4	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.4
Individuals	19.8	21.3	25.9	31.5	33.3
Other sectors	10.9	10.0	11.7	10.6	11.5
Total loans	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

It is evident from the data presented in Table 2 that, during 2020–2024, loans issued to industrial enterprises accounted for the largest share in the sectoral structure of loans provided by commercial banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The data in Table 2 also show that loans issued for material and technical supply, as well as for housing and communal services, accounted for a relatively small share in the sectoral structure of commercial bank loans during the analyzed period. This can be explained by the relatively low profitability of these sectors and the existence of state support mechanisms for them.

The above circumstances indicate the need to further diversify the loan portfolios of commercial banks by sectoral characteristics.

In order to deepen the analysis, the lending practices of JSC National Bank for Foreign Economic Activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan and JSCB “Asakabank” are examined below (Table 3).

Table 3
Amount and level of loans of the NBU “National Bank”³

Indicators	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Loans, billion soums	65,597.9	74,033.5	89,410.1	99,423.3	108,014.2
Share of loans in the volume of gross assets, %	82.1	82.3	74.6	78.0	80.0

As can be seen from the data presented in Table 3, loans accounted for a significant share of the total assets of the NBU “National Bank” during 2020–2024 [15].

However, during the analyzed period, the share of loans in gross assets showed a downward trend. This can be explained by the increase in the share of investments in securities within the structure of gross assets.

The data in Table 3 also indicate that the share of loans in the total assets of the NBU “National Bank” increased in 2020–2021, while the most significant decline in this indicator occurred in 2022 compared with 2021. In 2022–2024, the dynamics of this indicator reflected changes in the structure of the bank’s assets and the gradual diversification of its investment activities.

In order to continue the analysis, the lending practice of another commercial bank selected as a research object, JSCB “Asakabank”, is examined below (Table 4).

² author’s development

³ author’s development

Table 4
Amount and level of loans of JSCB “Asakabank” ⁴

Indicators	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Loans, billion soums	34,122.3	37,685.4	36,741.7	39,213.3	38,717.3
Share of loans in the volume of gross assets, %	75.0	74.2	71.8	67.6	66.6

The analysis of the data presented in Table 4 shows that, during 2020–2024, loans accounted for a significant share of the total assets of JSCB “Asakabank”. However, over the same period, the share of loans in total assets showed a declining trend [16]. This can be explained by the increase in the share of investments in securities within the bank’s asset structure during the analyzed period.

The data in Table 4 also show that the total volume of loans issued by JSCB “Asakabank” increased during 2020–2024. This trend can be considered positive from the perspective of improving the bank’s credit service practices.

The growth in the loan volume of JSCB “Asakabank” during 2020–2024 can be explained by the following three factors:

Active participation of JSCB “Asakabank” in state programs [7]. As a state-owned bank, Asakabank has actively participated in financing state programs, which played an important role in increasing the volume of its loans.

Increase in the prices of goods and services used as lending objects under the influence of inflation. Inflation-driven price increases in lending objects contributed to the growth of the loan volumes of commercial banks.

Depreciation of the national currency against foreign currencies [14]. As a result of exchange-rate depreciation, the national-currency equivalent of loans issued in foreign currencies increased at a relatively high rate.

Based on the data presented in Table 4, it can be concluded that the share of loans in the gross assets of JSCB “Asakabank” declined during 2020–2024. This was mainly due to the increase in the share of investments in securities and cash funds held in Nostro correspondent accounts within the structure of gross assets.

One of the indicators characterizing the improvement of banks’ credit services is the positive change in the structure of classified loans during the analyzed period (Table 5).

Table 5
Structure of classified loans of the NBU “National Bank”, in percent⁵

Indicators	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Standard loans	88.31	84.85	73.39	50.52	49.18
Substandard loans	8.86	10.69	23.66	46.36	47.79
Unsatisfactory loans	1.06	1.55	0.54	0.72	0.87
Doubtful loans	0.46	0.51	0.73	0.63	1.00
Hopeless loans	1.31	2.41	1.69	1.76	1.16
Total	100	100	100	100	100

The results of the analysis show that, according to the data presented in Table 4, the structure of classified loans of the NBU “National Bank” changed significantly during 2020–2024. In particular, in 2024, compared with 2020, the share of standard loans in the total volume of classified loans decreased by 39.13 percentage points. At the same time, the share of substandard loans increased by 38.93 percentage points.

⁴ author’s development

⁵ author’s development

During the analyzed period, the shares of unsatisfactory and hopeless loans in the total volume of classified loans showed unstable dynamics. In addition, the share of doubtful loans increased by 0.54 percentage points in 2024 compared with 2020 (Table 6).

Table 6

Amount and level of reserve allocations intended to cover losses from loans in the NBU “National Bank”⁶

Indicators	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Amount of reserve allocations intended to cover losses from loans, billion soums	1,536.3	2,881.5	3,012.1	6,116.7	5,359.7
Level of reserve allocations intended to cover losses from loans relative to gross assets (%)	1.9	3.2	2.5	4.8	4.0

As can be seen from the data in Table 5, during 2020–2024, the amount of reserve allocations intended to cover loan losses at the NBU “National Bank” and their share in total assets showed an upward trend. This situation can be explained by the changes in the structure of classified loans during the analyzed period.

An increase in the share of higher-risk classified loans leads to a rise in reserve allocations intended to cover possible loan losses. This, in turn, affects loan profitability and may reduce the amount of net profit.

Above, the structure of classified loans of the NBU “National Bank” was analyzed. The following table, Table 7, examines the structure of classified loans of JSCB “Asakabank”. It should also be emphasized that positive changes in the structure of classified loans during the analyzed period indicate an improvement in the quality of banks’ credit services (Table 7).

Table 7

Structure of classified loans of JSCB “Asakabank”, in percent⁷

Indicators	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Standard loans	86.91	92.03	85.95	93.80	92.24
Substandard loans	9.84	3.14	9.40	1.78	3.24
Unsatisfactory loans	0.67	3.20	2.66	3.27	4.25
Doubtful loans	1.04	0.81	1.33	1.07	0.20
Hopeless loans	1.54	0.82	0.66	0.08	0.07
Total	100	100	100	100	100

It can be seen from the data presented in Table 7 that the structure of classified loans of JSCB “Asakabank” changed positively during 2020–2024. In particular, in 2024, compared with 2020, the share of standard loans in the total volume of classified loans increased by 5.33 percentage points, while the share of hopeless loans decreased by 1.47 percentage points.

At the same time, the share of substandard loans decreased by 6.6 percentage points in 2024 compared with 2020. However, during the analyzed period, the share of unsatisfactory loans increased by 3.58 percentage points. The share of doubtful loans in the structure of classified loans showed unstable dynamics during 2020–2024 (Table 8).

⁶ author’s development

⁷ author’s development

Table 8

Amount and level of reserve allocations intended to cover losses from loans in JSCB "Asakabank" ⁸

Indicators	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Amount of reserve allocations intended to cover losses from loans, billion soums	1,234.4	1,326.0	1,315.4	1,393.3	1,073.9
Level of reserve allocations intended to cover losses from loans relative to gross assets (%)	2.7	2.6	2.6	2.4	1.8

As can be seen from the data presented in Table 8, during 2020–2024, the amount of reserve allocations intended to cover loan losses at JSCB "Asakabank" and their share in total assets showed a declining trend. This situation can be explained by the improvement in the structure of classified loans during the analyzed period.

An improvement in the structure of classified loans in the loan portfolio of commercial banks leads to a decrease in reserve allocations intended to cover possible loan losses. This, in turn, has a positive impact on loan profitability and contributes to an increase in net profit.

The depreciation of the national currency may increase the cost of credit resources and affect general economic and financial activity by raising the financial burden on the population, businesses, and entrepreneurs.

From this perspective, the dynamics of the nominal exchange rate of the national currency, the soum, against the US dollar are analyzed by year in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Nominal exchange rate of the national currency, the soum, against 1 US dollar, in soums⁹

As can be seen from the data presented in Figure 2, during 2020–2024, the depreciation of the national currency, the soum, against the US dollar remained significant and showed a steady upward trend. This led to a rapid increase in the national-currency equivalent of loans issued in foreign currency.

Another important indicator characterizing the development level of credit services is the ratio of reserve allocations intended to cover possible loan losses to total assets (Figure 2).

⁸ author's development

⁹ author's development

Figure 2. Level of reserve allocations intended to cover losses from loans relative to gross assets in JSCB "Asakabank" and the NBU "National Bank", %¹⁰

The data presented in Figure 2 show that, during 2020–2024, the ratio of reserve allocations intended to cover possible loan losses to total assets in JSCB "Asakabank" and the NBU "National Bank" was higher than the normative level of this indicator. The normative level of this indicator is considered to be 1.0%. This situation indicates the need to further improve the quality of credit services in these banks.

An increase in reserve allocations intended to cover possible loan losses may negatively affect the liquidity and financial stability of commercial banks. This is explained by two main factors. First, an increase in such allocations indicates a deterioration in the quality of the loan portfolio. Second, the growth of reserve allocations reduces the net profit of commercial banks, thereby limiting their capacity to expand lending and maintain financial stability (Table 9).

Table 9

Average interest rate on loans issued in national currency by commercial banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the refinancing rate of the Central Bank, and the annual inflation rate, in percent¹¹

Indicators	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Interest rate on commercial bank loans	22.3	20.8	21.9	23.1	23.7
Central Bank refinancing rate	14.0	14.0	15.0	15.0	14.0
Annual inflation rate	11.1	10.0	12.3	8.7	9.8

The analysis of the data presented in Table 9 shows that, during 2020–2024, the average annual interest rate on loans issued in the national currency by commercial banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan remained relatively high. Moreover, in 2024, this indicator increased significantly compared with 2020. From the perspective of improving banks' lending practices, this situation requires further attention [13].

As can be seen from Table 9, the refinancing rate of the Central Bank remained relatively high during 2020–2024. This can be explained by the high inflation rate observed during the same period. Under conditions of

¹⁰ author's development

¹¹ author's development

elevated inflation, the Central Bank has limited opportunities to reduce the refinancing rate, since an excessive reduction may contribute to further inflationary pressure.

The data in Table 9 also show that the inflation rate in the Republic of Uzbekistan remained high during 2020–2024. At the same time, in 2023–2024, inflation declined compared with 2020–2022. However, in 2024, the inflation rate increased by 1.1 percentage points compared with 2023.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Lending is one of the main areas of activity of commercial banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The role of banks in the development of the national economy is reflected primarily in their provision of credit resources to enterprises in the real sector of the economy.

One of the key issues of the credit mechanism is the establishment of requirements for loan collateral, including pledge collateral. Another important issue is the organization of reserve allocations intended to cover possible losses arising from loans.

During 2020–2024, loans accounted for the largest share of the total assets of commercial banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan. This indicates that lending remained the main direction of banking activity during the analyzed period.

In recent years, the practice of credit services provided by commercial banks in Uzbekistan has developed significantly [8]. Digitalization processes, state policy measures, and increasing competition among banks are contributing to the improvement of the efficiency of this sector. In the future, further improvement of the lending system will play an important role in ensuring sustainable economic growth.

REFERENCES

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On introducing amendments and additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan” № O’RQ-582 November 11, 2019. National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan <https://lex.uz/en/docs/6907475>
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On introducing amendments and additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On banks and banking activities” № O’RQ-580 November 5, 2019. National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. <https://lex.uz/en/docs/-4581969>
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Payments and Payment Systems” № O’RQ-578 November 1, 2019. National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/4575788>
4. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O’RQ-765 “On Non-Bank Credit Organizations and Microfinance Activities” April 20, 2022. National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. <https://lex.uz/en/docs/5972411>
5. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Leasing” № 756-I April 14, 1999. National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/4538319>
6. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Pledge Register” № O’RQ-356 June 12, 2014. National Database of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. <https://lex.uz/docs/6819316>
7. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4862 “On Improving the System of Involving the Population in Entrepreneurship and Additional Measures for the Development of Entrepreneurship.” October 13, 2020. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-5045889>
8. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5992 “On the Strategy for Reforming the Banking System of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2025.” May 12, 2020. <https://lex.uz/docs/-4811025>
9. Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Regulation “On the Procedure for Commercial Banks to Carry Out Syndicated Lending of Large Investment Projects” <https://cbu.uz/en/>
10. Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Instruction No. 2696 “On the Procedure for Classifying the Quality of Assets in Commercial Banks and Forming and Using Reserves to Cover Possible Losses on Assets.” July 14, 2015. <https://lex.uz/docs/2703056>
11. Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Banking System Performance Indicators: Official Statistical Data for 2020–2024.
12. Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Statistical Bulletin of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2020–2024.
13. Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Statistical Data on Interest Rates for Loans and Deposits in the National Currency. 2020–2024.

14. Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Archive of Foreign Exchange Rates: Nominal Exchange Rate of the Uzbek Soum Against the US Dollar, 2020–2024.
15. JSC National Bank for Foreign Economic Activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Annual Reports and Financial Statements. 2020–2024.
16. JSCB “Asakabank.” Annual Reports and Financial Statements. 2020–2024.
17. Mishkin, F. S. *The Economics of Money, Banking, and Financial Markets*. 13th ed. Pearson Education, 2019.

Proofreader: Xondamir Ismoilov
Layout and Designer: Hasan Maqsudov

2026. № 6

© When materials are reproduced, the ECONOSCITECH-INTEGRATION journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block, House 17.

